

CCAM Taxonomy: capturing gaps and barriers towards stakeholders' needs and requirements

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Abstract

Cooperative, Connected and Automated Mobility (CCAM) in the road transport sector is expected to reshape the way we move and travel. This paper aims to create a taxonomy for the domain of CCAM capturing the interrelationships between stakeholders' needs, requirements, goals and dilemmas with the gaps and barriers towards large-scale CCAM deployment. Literature and CCAM-related projects review has focused on recognizing the CCAM functional areas along with their purpose, building blocks and typical actors involved, identifying CCAM key enablers and investigating the effects and implications of large-scale CCAM deployment as well as, examining the gaps and barriers towards it. CCAM stakeholders' need and requirements and their respective goals and dilemmas are also classified. Finally, a critical assessment between gaps and barriers towards large-scale CCAM deployment and stakeholders' needs and requirements is presented. The analysis reveals the strong interrelationships in the domain of CCAM and useful insights for future CCAM deployment.

Keywords:

CCAM, Taxonomy

1. Introduction

Cooperative, Connected and Automated Mobility (CCAM) is at the forefront of the new digital era allowing the communication between vehicles, infrastructure, and road users. Its deployment aims to reduce congestion, and contributes to decarbonisation towards Vision Zero. Research into the CCAM field continues to articulate its potential to transform urban landscapes and existing transport systems and networks representing a socio-technical transition of the mobility system. Combining connectivity, cooperative systems and automation can enable smart traffic management, CCAM enabled shared mobility services integration with public transport and Mobility-as-a-Service (MaaS) platforms as well as automated public transport services. CCAM focuses and targets on user-centred, all-inclusive mobility while increasing safety [1].

This research is part of the EU funded SINFONICA project¹. An extensive literature and CCAM related projects review has been carried out in order to identify the enabling factors, including key enabling technologies, human-centered enablers and operators-centered enablers, effects and implications of as well as gaps and barriers towards CCAM large-scale deployment. Furthermore, research focused on identifying the CCAM stakeholders' needs and requirements, goals and dilemmas. Then, identified gaps and barriers towards CCAM were critically compared and assessed with these elements. The acquired knowledge and information, as well as insights from already existing taxonomies in the field of Intelligent Transport Systems (ITS) and CCAM, was finally structured as a unified taxonomy aiming to capture the inter-relationships in the CCAM ecosystem as a whole. Several instances of the taxonomy are presented in this paper, while the full taxonomy is available in Miro platform². Finally, a critical assessment between gaps and barriers towards large-scale CCAM deployment and stakeholders' needs and requirements is presented capturing the strong interrelationships in the domain of CCAM. Useful insights for future CCAM deployment and future work concludes this paper.

¹ <https://sinfonica.eu/>

² https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVMXA8OHU=/?share_link_id=572675334836

2. Related work – Taxonomies in ITS and CCAM

Society of Automotive Engineers (SAE) has published reports concerning terms and definitions related to cooperative driving automation for on-road motor vehicles [2], and taxonomy and definitions for terms related to driving automation systems for on-road motor vehicles [3]. INFRAMIX EU project has proposed a simple classification scheme to classify and harmonize the capabilities of road infrastructure to support and guide AVs [4]. Cledou et al. [5] proposed a taxonomy for planning and designing smart mobility services with the aim to serve as a tool for guiding policy makers by identifying a spectrum of mobility services that can be provided, to whom, what technologies can be used to deliver them, and what the delivered public value justifying their implementation is. Shibayama & Emberger [6] classified new and emerging mobility services based on the role of Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) for service conceptualization and the types of innovation. Castellanos et al. [7] proposed a taxonomy for shared mobility that can be used by policymakers, private stakeholders and academics in order to ensure a shared and common understanding of solutions under this term. Remane et al. [8] developed a taxonomy of carsharing business models. Damaj et al. [9] proposed a taxonomy for Quality of Experience (QoE) in Electric Connected and Automated Vehicles (CAVs) with a rich set of quality indicators and a framework that facilitates the integration of QoE concepts in system development. Gupta et al. [10] proposed a taxonomy focusing on the attacks on CAVs concerning the components and behaviour of CAVs, classifying them as attacks on authentication, communication and routing, data integrity, and data confidentiality. Furthermore, they proposed a blockchain-based CAV architecture to address CAVs' cybersecurity. Arthurs et al. [11] provided taxonomies for edge cloud computing use in ITS and Connected Vehicles (CV) as well as for their use cases.

3. Current practices of CCAM assets and services deployments

CCAM is a rapidly evolving field with significant potential to enhance mobility and safety. The CCAM ecosystem is a complex, multidisciplinary and interconnected network of stakeholders, technologies and infrastructure, all working together to create a safer and more efficient and sustainable transportation system. There are several projects underway to test and validate CCAM technologies in real-world settings aiming to identify potential issues and barriers to implementation, as well as demonstrate the benefits of CCAM to stakeholders and the public. Research in the field of CCAM in EU focuses in seven clusters: 1) key enabling technologies, 2) vehicle technologies, 3) integrating vehicles in the transport system, 4) societal aspects and user needs, 5) large-scale demonstrations, 6) validation and 7) coordination.³

3.1 CCAM functional areas and key enablers

CCAM incorporates all digital services and functions necessary to achieve viable, efficient, equitable and inclusive automated driving. A classification of the CCAM functional areas is presented in Table 1 taking into consideration all physical and digital aspects related to the CCAM ecosystem, along with their purpose, building blocks and actors involved as recognized by the European Commission standardization project EU-ICIP2⁴.

Table 1 – The CCAM functional areas

CCAM functional area	Purpose	Building blocks (Elements / Components / Technologies / Data (spaces))	Typical Actors
Digital enabled platforms	To provide platform-based transport services for citizens, corporations, academia, and governments.	Transport related digital platforms may be: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • MaaS platform • Parking solutions • Online travel agencies • Accommodations • Home deliveries • Digital freight platforms • Map solutions • Frontend systems for Personal ITS Station • Automated driving simulators for AI algorithm development through crowd sourcing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Government bodies • Medium Enterprises (SME) • International corporations • Non-profit organizations

³ <https://www.ccam.eu/projects/>

⁴ <https://www.mobilityits.eu/ccam-connected-vehicles>

CCAM Taxonomy: capturing gaps and barriers towards stakeholders' needs and requirements

CCAM functional area	Purpose	Building blocks (Elements / Components / Technologies / Data (spaces))	Typical Actors
Digital roads and associated infrastructure	To provide static and dynamic digital representations of the physical world with which CCAM vehicles interact (e.g., maps, traffic regulations, traffic, and travel information). May also include datasets collected from automated driving to be used in simulators.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> National Access Points Common European data spaces Traffic information Geographic information Lidar point clouds Whether data Public transport information Parking information MaaS data sharing Standardized test data from automated driving SOAP/REST Web Service API Message Queues solutions (e.g., AMQP, MQTT) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Government bodies: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Road and transport authorities Public transport City government National mapping agencies Whether services Small And Medium Enterprises (SME): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Parking services MaaS providers Roadside assistance International corporations: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Navigation system providers Auto manufacturers Non-profit organizations: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Aid organizations Environmental organizations
Operational road infrastructure	To provide fleet and traffic management functions which facilitate traffic flow by issuing information or guidance including tele-operated driving of automated vehicles, concierge services and eCall Public Safety Answering Point (PSAP).	Operational control systems may be: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Regional Traffic Management Centres Vehicle Original Equipment Manufacturer system with navigation functionality Fleet management Automated Road Maintenance Management systems Tele-operation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Vehicle manufactures and navigation systems providers Fleet operators (including operators of automated vehicles) Tele-operation centres Traffic management centres
Physical road infrastructure	To allow vehicles and people to move in an efficient and seamless way from point to point. It can expand the Operational Design Domain (ODD) of automated driving functions by providing additional sensory input for the vehicles by means of roadside mounted cameras, radars, and whether stations, as well as status information from tunnels and bridges.	It comprises the physical world where vehicles operate including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> roads road signs road markings pavements parking / drop-off areas sensors physical communication infrastructure equipment enhanced positioning infrastructure. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Transport authorities Road operators Road construction and maintenance contractors Toll road operators C-ITS infrastructure providers Mobile network operators Providers of enhanced positioning solutions Weather services Charging station providers Parking providers
Vehicle technologies	Focuses on in-vehicle technologies for connected and automated vehicles (CAVs) that will improve perception, prediction, and planning functions, enable safe collaboration with other road users, and activate protective measures in case of emergency.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Standardization of sensing devices Infrastructure-based sensing and sensor fusion Cooperative perception Distilled AI functions for on-board decision making Cooperative manoeuvres Standardized human machine interaction (HMI) Assess chauffeur and logging of accident data Automatic call for help Sharing of vehicle data with the digital road infrastructure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Manufactures of vehicles with automated driving functionality Suppliers of components and solutions for automated driving Vehicle type approval authorities and authorized technical services organizations Fleet operators of automated vehicles Road operators and road construction and maintenance contractors using automated road maintenance machines Tele-operation centres used as fall-back solutions for automated vehicle stranded outside their Operational Design Domain (ODD)
Communication, cyber security and Privacy	To enable secure, seamless, efficient, robust communications between on-road devices, vehicles, infrastructure and other road users.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Public Key Infrastructure (PKI) authentication and verification of exchanged data Hardware security module (HSM) for storing of certificates, intrusion detection and response, secure software updates, and General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) compliance 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Industry <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Automobile manufacturers Automotive suppliers ITS solution providers Telecom industry Mobile network operators Cloud providers Government <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Transport authorities Road authorities

CCAM functional area	Purpose	Building blocks (Elements / Components / Technologies / Data (spaces))	Typical Actors
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wireless communication (e.g., short-range ITS-G5, long-range cellular communication) • Communication protocols (e.g., HTTP, AMQP, MQTT) • C-ITS hybrid communication • Authentication standards (e.g., FIDO, OAuth) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Road operators ○ Emergency responders • Service providers ○ Roadside assistance ○ Public transport ○ Mobility and logistics providers ○ Insurance companies ○ Toll road operators

The Strategic Transport Research and Innovation Agenda (STRIA), was adopted in 2017 by the European Commission, and states the main R&I priorities intending to clean, connected and competitive mobility [12]. Furthermore, TRIMIS (Transport Research and Innovation Monitoring and Information System) is utilized as a transport R&I database where a regular reporting on evolving and future technologies is created [13]. Respectively, several key enabling technologies are recognized, including Artificial Intelligence (AI), simulation and Digital Twins, and Internet of Vehicles (IoV) among others. Furthermore, several enabling factors for CCAM operators and deployers are recognized in the literature and CCAM-related projects, e.g., the operation of Traffic Management Centres and remote-control rooms, surveillance and sensing, data management and the maturity of technology. Lastly, human-centred and non-technological enablers focus on collaborative schemes, growth of digital skills and familiarization with new technologies, meeting citizens' mobility needs in terms of accessibility, availability, affordability and acceptability, the on-board presence of personnel and more. All key enablers for large-scale CCAM deployment are classified and reported in Figure 1.

Figure 1 – Enabling factors towards CCAM large-scale deployment

4. Towards large-scale CCAM deployment

The CCAM ecosystem is a complex, multidisciplinary and interconnected network of stakeholders, technologies and infrastructure, all working together to create a safer and more efficient and sustainable transportation system. The following sections aim to capture the effects and implications from large-scale CCAM deployment. Respectively a SWOT (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats) analysis is performed. Furthermore, gaps and barriers towards large-scale CCAM deployment are examined and reported.

4.1 Strengths and opportunities

CCAM is expected to improve traffic safety and reduce accidents caused by human error as highlighted at a significant number of studies [14]. Most studies, deploying simulation models, reveal that the full potential of benefits would be achieved with high Automated Vehicles (AVs) penetration rates [15]. Large-scale usage of AVs could prove beneficial for non-car-based mobility like public transport services, creating an opportunity window for sustainability [16]. A thoroughly studied positive aspect of AVs is the limitation of the total number of vehicles in road networks, since AVs can be utilized in car-sharing and ride-sharing services [17].

Connectedness of CAVs can help at handling flows optimally, utilizing cooperation of vehicles and infrastructure, like adaptive signaling and prioritization of public transport vehicles, leading to traffic optimization [18].

Further urban sprawl can also be achieved due to the improved accessibility that AVs are expected to provide at suburban areas; Low-income people seem to be more significantly affected, since they will have easier access and connection to urban centres, without being forced to live there [19]. People with mobility challenges are also expected to enhance their mobility due to the increased accessibility and freedom they will be experiencing [20]. Parking lots and facilities could be reshaped to cover less space and relocated out of city centre, since parking demand will be significantly limited there [21]. The authorities of each city where AVs will be fully penetrated into, may use the previously occupied parking places for housing and commercial land uses [22], while city outskirts and suburbs will be sprawling even more due to better time utilization by potential users who prefer suburban regions [23].

Although one could only project and anticipate what could happen in the financial sector once CCAM will be an implemented reality, studies showcase that by 2030 the expected revenues are going to be doubled in the USA; 40% of them are savings from collisions avoidance, 15% is gained due to fuel limitation, and another 45% from productivity increase [24]. Job fields like software engineering, decision-making, vehicle cybersecurity and data engineering are expected to see a boost in demand in the forthcoming years [25].

4.2 Weaknesses and Threats

On the other hand, several negative implications can be recognized as well. There is a risk of increased traffic demand on city centre road network, since commuting trips are anticipated to be scheduled and operated more often with the use of personal AVs [26]. Empty trips or 'empty-cruising' of AVs has been connected with a significant increase in parking demand in suburban areas and unnecessary trips within central areas. AVs will probably be encouraged to circulate in low speed around the city centre and may not even decide to park at all until a new ride request is on [27]. It is also possible that AVs will gain passengers from existent public transportation, which is not necessarily beneficial in terms of congestion [28]. It is highly possible that on-demand AVs will conduce to a less athletic general population, since users will be able to commute walking the least possible or without walking at all. Dispersed urban growth, which has been stated as an outcome of the wide AVs implementation is also a restrictive factor when it comes to active travel, like cycling or walking, because of the long routes connecting a suburban homeplace with the city centre [29]. Another valid safety concern, at least until the stage of full CCAM deployment, could be the difficulties in co-existence of AVs with conventional vehicles [30]. The coexistence of AVs and conventional vehicles might slightly worsen traffic safety [31]. Nevertheless, studies conducted in this research area are unsure about the possibility of large-scale penetration of AVs in countries or regions with low median income as means of individual transport. If citizens of these areas cannot afford such services, societal impacts such as enhancing the gap between rich and poor, will be evident [32]. Social gaps in terms of educational levels might be enhanced too, since technologically illiterate or lowly educated citizens will feel falling behind their co-citizens [33].

Financial drawbacks are not easily predictable although many studies have been conducted in this field. Albright et al. [34] estimated that insurance companies could suffer 60% economic losses due to the positive impact CCAM is anticipated to have on safety. Society-wise, many people with low level of education or middle-aged ones, who will become unemployed, since their jobs will cease to exist, might encounter difficulties into getting another job, due to lack of qualifications combined with the increasing demand for high-qualified persons in the AV reality marketplace [35]. A far from insignificant barrier of public acceptance of CCAM, and therefore a challenge to be mitigated, is the users' perception of losing control of movement, entrusting it to algorithms they cannot see or interact with taking also into account the increase in cybercrime [36].

In terms of legislation, since CCAM constitutes a novel aspect of mobility, issues associated to it, arise. The most complex and important one seems to be the liability in case of an accident, while responsibility and accountability issues also constitute a challenge to be addressed especially in the case of shared automated mobility services [37]. The SWOT analysis based on the above positive and negative possible implications is presented in Table 2.

4.3 Gaps and barriers towards large-scale CCAM deployment

Several challenges need to be addressed in order to achieve large-scale CCAM deployment. Based on CCAM projects and literature review these challenges are mostly associated with ICT, Safety, User-centric factors (especially public acceptance) and legislative and regulatory aspects. This is also confirmed by Bezai et al. [38]

Table 2 – SWOT analysis

Strengths	Opportunities	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cooperation • Connectivity • Automation • Mobility on Demand • Mobility-as-a-Service • Personalized services • Real-time data • Human error elimination • Free of driving task • Direct emergency response • Positive effect on industries/sectors 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improved safety • Increased traffic efficiency • Improved infrastructure capacity • Improved quality of life • Environmental sustainability • Increased revenues and cost savings • Improved traffic management • Services optimization • First and last-mile services • New business models 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New job opportunities • Investment and growth opportunities • Urban sprawl and improved urban planning • Inclusivity and Equity • Accessibility • People with mobility challenges independency • Personal time utilization
Weaknesses	Threats	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High initial cost • Limited deployment • Technology and safety gaps • Empty trips • Mixed traffic conditions until full-deployment • Ambiguous legal environment • Cyber-vulnerability • Negative effects on industries/sectors • Lack of familiarization with automation • Lack of trust • Lack of personal space • Need for digital skills 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Abrupt CCAM deployment • Safety implications • Increased energy consumption • Reduced traffic efficiency • Unexpected/unpredicted situations • Social gap enlargement • Public transport depreciation • Liability and accountability issues • Cybersecurity and privacy risks • Unwillingness for data sharing • Infrastructure challenges 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Economic implications • Potential job displacement / Unemployment • Active travel discouragement • Non-acceptance

who conducted research regarding the analysis of barriers to AVs full adoption. The following sections are based on the projects' review as well as on Bezai et al. (2021) findings aiming to address the most critical aspects towards CCAM large-scale deployment.

4.3.1 Information and Communication Technologies (ICT)

Two techniques are currently implemented for the communication between actors in the CCAM ecosystem, ITS-G5 and cellular communication. 5G is expected to provide high speed communication achieving the required latency for several critical operations of CAVs. IoV can facilitate communication between vehicles, infrastructure, and other road users, integrating computing and communication modules. To ensure on-road safety, it is critical to maximise the Quality of Service (QoS) in IoV in terms of security, system failure, signal strength and latency. Data dissemination and routing, data integration and operational management, and security and privacy are key challenges that need to be addressed in order to achieve the desired efficiency, reliability and safety of communication and cooperation. Another challenge is the infrastructure cost for communication. Furthermore, IoV is inherently vulnerable to security threats concerning the integrity, confidentiality and availability of data [39].

Several hardware equipment is utilized by AVs in order to achieve the desired perception of the environment, plan their behaviour and decide on how to proceed. Furthermore, software embedding advanced algorithms and techniques like machine learning and neural networks are integrated into the system aiming to achieve optimal performance of automated driving [40]. Nevertheless, when it comes to hardware systems, they are inherently prone to system failure. Thus, the systems' uninterrupted function is another critical issue that needs imperatively to be addressed. Furthermore, components' interoperability is not yet fully understood and cost may be excessive. It is critical that optimal performance of all components is achieved as well as data fusion from all sources is comprehensively addressed. Lastly, the huge amount of data that CAVs are expected to produce, requires powerful computers and big data storage spaces. [38].

Focusing on navigation of CAVs, connectivity has the potential to bring new intelligence to CAVs related to their environment and surroundings enhancing this way various driving aspects [41]. Localization and mapping are considered crucial aspects for optimal vehicle navigation and research is undergone in the field. Simultaneous localization and mapping (SLAM) is considered a promising technique to address this issue based on a hybrid approach [42]. Advanced algorithms are also developed to address the problem of path planning [41][43].

4.3.2 Safety

The way AVs are expected to behave while interacting with other vehicles and road users is still a matter of

research. A unified approach is considered critical in order to ensure the compatibility of all vehicle types with the CCAM ecosystem [44]. Interoperability and standardization of technical components and interfaces is widely recognized as a requirement in order to facilitate CCAM large-scale deployment. Communication is another critical technological brick of CCAM and significant advances are expected in the recent future. Research is currently focused on safety standards, fusion systems, sensors, and HMIs and advances are also expected to enhance their performance and achieve the desired quality. Gaps are also recognized concerning big data management and the required computation power to process them.

Infrastructure adaption will require high initial cost in order to ensure safety for the operation of CAVs. Furthermore, new traffic management will be required and there is a research focus on addressing how CAVs will cooperate with the Traffic Management Centre. Infrastructure may also be vulnerable to externalities causes either by natural causes or human and external interference (e.g., vandalism). These are issues that need to be imperatively addressed in order to ensure the safety of operations of all components of the infrastructure. Lastly, the regulatory framework regarding the obligations of infrastructure players is still missing.

Shareability is expected to boost CCAM's benefits to its full potential. Yet, it encompasses some risks. Several issues that are critical to be addressed concerning shared mobility concern flexibility in schedules and coordination, risk of attacks and insurance problems [45]. Furthermore, lack of personal space may be a barrier towards large-scale deployment while discussion is also focused on the safety regulations accompanied with rear seat designated to children. Thus, parents may be reluctant to use shared mobility options [46].

4.3.3 Users' acceptance

From a user perspective, AVs and CCAM could experience barriers in terms of acceptance and usage. Future CCAM public transport systems, such as SAVs and mobility on demand, are expected to mitigate transport poverty and provide opportunities for improved accessibility and availability of transportation options [47]. Users' expectations, perception, and acceptance of AVs present great variations in research studies [44][48]. Accordingly, perceived safety and reliability of AVs as well as the uncertainty of moral decision-making by AVs are prominent factors that might affect AVs' widespread public acceptance and lead to mistrust and skepticism. The purchase price of individual AVs as well as shared and on-demand mobility services deploying AVs will play crucial role in public acceptance and willingness to pay. Of course, willingness to pay and use will also depend on the effectiveness and reliability of the technology as well as on the accessibility to the technology and services [49][50].

Several researchers examined the acceptance and acceptability of shared automated vehicles and although there is no consensus about how socio-economic and demographic variables will influence the large-scale deployment of CCAM, they should certainly be further researched, as will be done in the SINFONICA co-creation steps, since several variables seem to have diverse effects [51].

4.3.4 Regulatory and legislative framework

The lack of a common framework for AV deployment may have significant impact on AV safety and security [52]. Furthermore, clear and fair distribution of responsibilities, obligations, culpability, accountability and liability across the different actors is identified as a key aspect to be addressed in order to ensure safety of AVs and public acceptance [44]. However, the immaturity of and public trust in the existing technologies are considered as barriers in formulating regulations. Policies for CCAM deployment should encourage R&D innovation ensuring at the same time safety and reliability, and paving the way towards public trust and acceptance [52]. Furthermore, this situation triggers changes to the insurance framework which is necessary to take into consideration the shift in liability from drivers to CAVs, data sharing issues and the shared mobility market [53]. Nevertheless, Merriman et al. [54] have recognized several gaps in the current training for drivers of AVs.

Cybersecurity and data privacy regulations are essential to any ICT infrastructure. Great efforts are made to address cybersecurity and data privacy issues concerning ITS, CAVs and IoV. The production of huge amount of data, most of which may be considered personal data, may affect potential CCAM users' attitude and impact negatively to CCAM large-scale deployment [55]. Table 3 presents the aggregated results from the gaps and barriers towards large-scale CCAM deployment analysis.

6. CCAM stakeholders' needs and requirements

CCAM ecosystem encompass strong and complex interrelations between its stakeholders and their respective needs and requirements, as well as their goals and dilemmas. An attempt to classify CCAM stakeholders' needs

Table 3 – Gaps and barriers towards large-scale CCAM deployment

Field		Gaps and barriers	
ICT	Connectivity & communication systems	Latency IoV Communication protocols Security & privacy	Quality of Service Financial cost Lack of Infrastructure Signal reliability
	Software & Hardware	Interoperability System failure Sensors' performance Big data Processing speed and transfer Data storage Communication	Cost Cybersecurity Advanced algorithms <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Perception • Data fusion • Planning • Decision-making
	Navigation	Connectivity and Communication Latency Positioning Mapping Sensors Advanced algorithms	Object recognition and avoidance Data fusion Path planning Decision making Safety performance
Safety	CAVs' performance	Common approach to safety behaviour of CAVs	Interaction of CAVs with other road users
	Technology	Interoperability Standardization Communication systems Fusion systems	Sensors Big data Recognition Computation power
	Infrastructure	Cost Traffic management Vulnerability of infrastructure	Infrastructure requirements Regulatory framework
	Shareability	Risk of attacks Personal space Insurance issues	Suitability for children Ownership Accessibility
Users' acceptance	Perception	Perceived safety Reliability & Ethics Socio-economic and demographics Security and privacy	Personal data sharing Distrust Unaware of CCAM real benefits Unfamiliarity
	CAVs' performance and services	Transparency of intention of CAVs Liability of passengers Unwillingness to use Shared mobility	Unwillingness to use if decision making is not based on protecting the passengers
	Cost	Shared services cost	Individual vehicles cost
Regulatory and legislative framework	Certifications / regulations	Common framework for CCAM deployment Certification model for cybersecurity & data privacy Open data policies Standards for safety behaviour of CAVs System failure	Clear and fair distribution of obligations, culpability and liability Insurance framework Training for drivers of CAVs (type of driving license) Immaturity of technology Public trust
	Ethics	Standards for ethical and safety design principles of CAVs	User acceptance Models and algorithms for ethical reasoning and choice

and requirements as well as their respective goals and dilemmas into organizational/operational, technical, regulatory/legal, financial and social is presented in Figures 2 and 3.

Gaps and barriers can be strongly interrelated with the stakeholders' needs, requirements, goals and dilemmas. Focusing on the ICT barriers, if comprehensively addressed, they can pave the way towards large-scale CCAM deployment. For example, if connectivity and communication systems are capable to ensure the desired reliability and security of the CCAM system, achieving at the same time the required latency for critical applications, safety demonstrations of CCAM solutions, which is considered an important factor towards validation of CCAM and users' acceptance, will be potentially feasible in more unpredictable and complex real-world scenarios. Furthermore, interoperability and standardization of components, interfaces and services would enable stakeholders to effectively and efficiently achieve the integration of CCAM assets into their infrastructure and road network in a cost-efficient way. Focusing on navigation, the standardization and optimization of Operational Design Domain (ODD) could act as an enabler to achieve the desired CAVs' performance. Respectively, EC has released rules regarding uniform procedures and technical specifications for the type-approval of the Automated Driving System (ADS) of fully automated vehicles addressing ADS performance requirements [56]. Furthermore, EC has laid down harmonised rules of AI which is a rapidly developing field that requires novel forms of regulatory oversight and a safe space of experimentation, while ensuring responsible innovation and integration of appropriate safeguards and risk mitigation measure. Thus, Member States should

CCAM Taxonomy: capturing gaps and barriers towards stakeholders' needs and requirements

Figure 2 – CCAM stakeholders' needs and requirements classification

Figure 3 – CCAM stakeholders' goals, challenges and dilemmas classification

be encouraged to establish AI regulatory sandboxes to facilitate the development and testing of AI systems under strict regulatory oversight before they are publicly available [57].

Demonstrating a common CAVs safety behaviour approach as well as safety of the CCAM technology, ensuring the safe interactions between all road users, will foster CCAM deployment. Adoption of the infrastructure as well as related cost and safety implications are also addressed both from the perspective of barriers and gaps as well as needs to be addressed for CCAM stakeholders. Safety of shared services are also interrelated with the stakeholders' need to ensure the safety of operations and should therefore be comprehensively addressed. The same is also considered about traffic management which needs to be adapted and reformed taking into consideration CCAM requirements and stakeholders needs and expectations. The future of CCAM will finally rely on the users' acceptance. Users' perception will strongly rely on their experience, knowledge and familiarization with CCAM. Perceived safety, reliability and ethics are some factors that have an effect on users' acceptance and may lead to distrust and non-willingness to use CCAM solutions. On the other hand, if fully aware of the benefits that CCAM has the potential to bring, they might be positively affected towards using CCAM solutions. Building knowledge and providing training schemes and public awareness campaigns are already realized for addressing users' acceptance related risks.

7. Conclusions & future work

Research in the field of CCAM has already provided useful insights about the potential that CCAM has in order to contribute to a safer, more efficient, sustainable, equitable and inclusive transportation system. The anticipated benefits are considered to overbalance the related risks related to large-scale CCAM deployment. Users' acceptance is expected to be the ultimate factor that will decide CCAM's future and deployment. Aspects regarding users' perception of CCAM will certainly have an effect on their willingness to use CCAM services. Undoubtedly, this will also rely on the performance of CAVs taking into consideration aspects like transparency in CAVs' intentions and decision making, liability issues as well as the quality of services. Certainly, the adjustment of legislation is considered both as an enabler towards large-scale CCAM deployment and a critical issue yet to be comprehensively addressed. The CCAM taxonomy will constitute the basis for the SINFONICA Knowledge Map Explorer, which will constitute an innovative tool that will facilitate the effective and efficient knowledge sharing between CCAM stakeholders by providing recommendations and guidelines on best practices towards CCAM deployments based on the specific user type, context and request.

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References

1. CCAM Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (v1.4), March 2022
2. SAE International (2021a). J3016_202104: Taxonomy and Definitions for Terms Related to Driving Automation Systems for On-Road Motor Vehicles.
3. SAE International (2021b). J 3216_202107: Taxonomy and Definitions for Terms related to Cooperative Driving Automation for On-Road Motor Vehicles.
4. Carreras, A., Xavier, D., Erhart, J. & Ruehrup, S. (2018). Road infrastructure support levels for automated driving, *25th ITS World Congress*, pp. 12–20.
5. Cledou, G., Estevez, E., & Soares Barbosa, L. (2017). A taxonomy for planning and designing smart mobility services. *Government Information Quarterly*, 35 (1), 61–76. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.giq.2017.11.008>
6. Shibayama, T., & Emberger, G. (2020). New mobility services: Taxonomy, innovation and the role of ICTs. *Transport Policy*, 98, 79–90. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tranpol.2020.05.024>
7. Castellanos, S., Grant-Muller, S., & Wright, K. (2022). Technology, transport, and the sharing economy: towards a working taxonomy for shared mobility. *Transport Reviews*, 42 (3), 318–336. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01441647.2021.1968976>
8. Remane, G., Nickerson, R. C., Hanelt, A., Tesch, J. F., & Kolbe, L. M. (2016). A Taxonomy of Carsharing Business Models. In *37th International Conference on Information Systems*, Dublin, 2016
9. Damaj, I. W., Serhal, D. K., Hamandi, L. A., Zantout, R. N., & Mouftah, H. T. (2021). Connected and Autonomous Electric Vehicles: Quality of Experience survey and taxonomy. *Vehicular Communications*, 28. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vehcom.2020.100312>
10. Gupta, R., Kumari, A., & Tanwar, S. (2021). A taxonomy of blockchain envisioned edge-as-a-connected autonomous vehicles. *Transactions on Emerging Telecommunications Technologies*, 32 (6). <https://doi.org/10.1002/ett.4009>
11. Arthurs, P., Gillam, L., Krause, P., Wang, N., Halder, K., & Mouzakitis, A. (2022). A Taxonomy and Survey of Edge Cloud Computing for Intelligent Transportation Systems and Connected Vehicles. *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, 23 (7), 6206–6221. <https://doi.org/10.1109/TITS.2021.3084396>
12. European Commission. (2018). On the road to automated mobility: An EU strategy for mobility of the future (communication from the commission to the European parliament, the Council, the European economic and social committee and the committee of the regions COM (2018)).
13. Tsakalidis, A., Gkoumas, K., Pekar, F., Grosso, M., Haq, G., & Marelli, L. (2018). Towards an integrated European platform for monitoring and analysing transport research and innovation (TRIMIS). *Proceedings of 7th Transport Research Arena TRA*, 16-19.
14. Han, Y., Chen, D., & Ahn, S. (2017). Variable speed limit control at fixed freeway bottlenecks using connected vehicles. *Transportation Research Part B: Methodological*, 98, 113-134.
15. Papadimitriou, E., Farah, H., van de Kaa, G., Santoni de Sio, F., Hagenzieker, M., & van Gelder, P. (2022). Towards common ethical and safe 'behaviour' standards for automated vehicles. *Accident Analysis and*

- Prevention*, 174. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aap.2022.106724>
16. Schippl, J., Truffer, B., & Fleischer, T. (2022). Potential impacts of institutional dynamics on the development of automated vehicles: Towards sustainable mobility? *Transportation Research Interdisciplinary Perspectives*, 14. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trip.2022.100587>
 17. Fagnant, D., & Kockelman, K. (2014). The travel and environmental implications of shared autonomous vehicles, using agent-based model scenarios. *Transportation Research Part C: Emerging Technologies*, 40, 1–13.
 18. Dresner, K., & Stone, P. (2004). Multiagent traffic management: A reservation-based intersection control mechanism. In *Autonomous Agents and Multiagent Systems, International Joint Conference on* (Vol. 3, pp. 530-537). IEEE Computer Society.
 19. Meyer, J., Becker, H., Bösch, P. M., & Axhausen, K. W. (2017). Autonomous vehicles: The next jump in accessibilities?. *Research in transportation economics*, 62, 80-91.
 20. Brown, A., Gonder, J., & Repac, B. (2014). An analysis of possible energy impacts of automated vehicles. *Road vehicle automation*, 137-153.
 21. Nourinejad, M., Bahrami, S. & Roorda, M. J. (2018). Designing parking facilities for autonomous vehicles. *Transportation Research Part B: Methodological*, 109, 110-127.
 22. Llorca, C., Moreno, A., Ammar, G., & Moeckel, R. (2022). Impact of autonomous vehicles on household relocation: An agent-based simulation. *Cities*, 126, 103692.
 23. Hiramatsu, T. (2022). Impact of autonomous vehicles on the choice of residential locality. *Transportation planning and technology*, 45(3), 268-288.
 24. Römer, M., Gaenzle, S., & Weiss, C. (2016). How automakers can survive the self-driving era. *AT Kearney*. Online Available: <https://www.atkearney.com/automotive/article>.
 25. Clements, L. M., & Kockelman, K. M. (2017). Economic Effects of Automated Vehicles. *Transportation Research Record*, 2606(1), 106–114.
 26. Aittoniemi, E, Barnard, Y, Harrison, G, De Klein, D, Kolarova, V, Lehtonen, E, Malin, F, Naendruppoel, L, Rama, P & Toulou, K. (2020). AUTOPILOT (AUTOMated driving Progressed by Internet Of Things). D.4.6: Quality of Life Impact Assessment.
 27. Millard-Ball, A. (2019). The autonomous vehicle parking problem. *Transport Policy*, 75, 99-108.
 28. Metz, D. (2018). Developing policy for urban autonomous vehicles: Impact on congestion. *Urban Science*, 2 (2), 33.
 29. Oh, S., Seshadri, R., Azevedo, C. L., Kumar, N., Basak, K., & Ben-Akiva, M. (2020). Assessing the impacts of automated mobility-on-demand through agent-based simulation: A study of Singapore. *Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice*, 138, 367-388.
 30. Innamaa, S., Smith, S., Barnard, Y., Rainville, L., Rakoff, H., Horiguchi, R., & Gellerman, H. (2018). Trilateral impact assessment framework for automation in road transportation. *Tech. Rep.*
 31. Schoettle, B., & Sivak, M. (2015). Potential impact of self-driving vehicles on household vehicle demand and usage. University of Michigan, Ann Arbor, Transportation Research Institute.
 32. Wadud, Z., MacKenzie, D., & Leiby, P. (2016). Help or hindrance? The travel, energy and carbon impacts of highly automated vehicles. *Transportation Research Part A: Policy and Practice*, 86, 1–18.
 33. Clark, B. Y., Larco, N., & Mann, R. F. (2017). The impacts of autonomous vehicles and e-commerce on local government budgeting and finance. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. Doi:10.2139/ssrn.3009840
 34. Albright, J., Bell, A., Schneider, J., & Nyce, C. (2015). Automobile insurance in the era of autonomous vehicles. *KPMG LLP, Amstelveen*.
 35. Harrison, G., Stanford, J., Rakoff, H., Smith, S., Shepherd, S., Barnard, Y., & Innamaa, S. (2022). Assessing the influence of connected and automated mobility on the liveability of cities. *Journal of Urban Mobility*, 2, 100034. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.urbmob.2022.100034>
 36. Hui, K. L., Kim, S. H., & Wang, Q. H. (2017). Cybercrime Deterrence and International Legislation. *Mis Quarterly*, 41(2), 497-524.
 37. Gleave, S. D., Frisoni, R., Dall'Oglio, A., Nelson, C., Long, J., Vollath, C., ... & McMinimy, S. (2016). Research for TRAN-committee–Self-piloted Cars: the Future of Road Transport. Requested by the European Parliament's Committee on Transport and Tourism.
 38. Bezai, N. E., Medjdoub, B., Al-Habaibeh, A., Chalal, M. L., & Fadli, F. (2021). Future cities and autonomous vehicles: analysis of the barriers to full adoption. *Energy and Built Environment*, 2(1), 65–81. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbenv.2020.05.002>
 39. Tabassum, N., & Reddy, C. R. K. (2022). Review on QoS and security challenges associated with the

- internet of vehicles in cloud computing. *Measurement: Sensors*, 100562. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.measen.2022.100562>
40. Pendleton, S. D., Andersen, H., Du, X., Shen, X., Meghjani, M., Eng, Y. H., Rus, D., & Ang, M. H. (2017). Perception, planning, control, and coordination for autonomous vehicles. *Machines*, 5(1). <https://doi.org/10.3390/machines5010006>
 41. Typaldos, P., Papageorgiou, M., & Papamichail, I. (2022). Optimization-based path-planning for connected and non-connected automated vehicles. *Transportation Research Part C: Emerging Technologies*, 134. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trc.2021.103487>
 42. Prasad, A. O., Mishra, P., Jain, U., Pandey, A., Sinha, A., Yadav, A. S., Kumar, R., Sharma, A., Kumar, G., Hazim Salem, K., Sharma, A., & Dixit, A. K. (2023). Design and development of software stack of an autonomous vehicle using robot operating system. *Robotics and Autonomous Systems*, 161. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.robot.2022.104340>
 43. Diachuk, M., & Easa, S. M. (2022). Motion Planning for Autonomous Vehicles Based on Sequential Optimization. *Vehicles*, 4(2), 344–374. <https://doi.org/10.3390/vehicles4020021>
 44. Papadimitriou, E., Farah, H., van de Kaa, G., Santoni de Sio, F., Hagenzieker, M., & van Gelder, P. (2022). Towards common ethical and safe 'behaviour' standards for automated vehicles. *Accident Analysis and Prevention*, 174. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aap.2022.106724>
 45. Aguiléra, A. (2019). Smart phone and Individual Travel Behavior. *Urban Mobility and the Smartphone*, Elsevier Inc., pp.1–37, <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-812647-9.00001-9>
 46. Grush, B. & Niles, J. (2018). Barriers to Shared Use of Vehicles, *End of Driving*. Elsevier, pp. 125–139, doi:10.1016/B978-0-12-815451-9.00009-2
 47. Shaheen, S. A., Cohen, A. P., Broader, J., Hoban, S., Auer, A., Cordahi, G., & Kimmel, S. (2022). *Shared automated vehicle toolkit: Policies and planning considerations for implementation*. NCHRP research report: Vol. 1009. Transportation Research Board. <https://doi.org/10.17226/26821>
 48. Othman, K. (2021). Public acceptance and perception of autonomous vehicles: a comprehensive review. *AI and Ethics*, 1 (3), 355–387. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43681-021-00041-8>
 49. Webb, J., Wilson, C., & Kularatne, T. (2019). Will people accept shared autonomous electric vehicles? A survey before and after receipt of the costs and benefits. *Economic Analysis and Policy*, 61, 118–135. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eap.2018.12.004>
 50. Bansal, P., Kockelman, K. M., & Singh, A. (2016). Assessing public opinions of and interest in new vehicle technologies: An Austin perspective. *Transportation Research Part C: Emerging Technologies*, 67, 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trc.2016.01.019>
 51. de Paepe, L., van Acker, V., & Witlox, F. (2023). To share or not to share, by whom is the question. Acceptability and acceptance of shared transport services by vulnerable groups. *Transport Reviews*, 1–35. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01441647.2023.2185314>
 52. Li, S., Sui, P.-C., Xiaoa, J., Chahine, R., 2019. Policy formulation for highly automated vehicles: emerging importance, research frontiers and insights. *Transp. Res. Part A* 124 (2019), 573–586.
 53. Kester, J. (2022). Insuring future automobility: A qualitative discussion of British and Dutch car insurer's responses to connected and automated vehicles. *Research in Transportation Business and Management*, 45. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rtbm.2022.100903>
 54. Merriman, S. E., Plant, K. L., Revell, K. M. A., & Stanton, N. A. (2021). Challenges for automated vehicle driver training: A thematic analysis from manual and automated driving. *Transportation Research Part F: Traffic Psychology and Behaviour*, 76, 238–268. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trf.2020.10.011>
 55. Benyahya, M., Collen, A., Kechagia, S., & Nijdam, N. A. (2022). Automated city shuttles: Mapping the key challenges in cybersecurity, privacy and standards to future developments. *Computers and Security*, 122. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cose.2022.102904>
 56. European Commission (2022). Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2022/1426 of 5 August 2022 laying down rules for the application of Regulation (EU) 2019/2144 of the European Parliament and of the Council as regards uniform procedures and technical specifications for the type-approval of the automated driving system (ADS) of fully automated vehicles.
 57. European Commission (2021). Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council laying down harmonised rules on Artificial Intelligence (Artificial Intelligence Act) and amending certain Union Legislative Acts.